

SMART-AI: ASSESSMENT OF SMART BEEHIVES USING SENSOR SYSTEMS AND THEIR IMPACT ON COLONY CONDITION

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Abstract. *This article presents data on real-time measurements of internal hive conditions in smart beehives using sensor-based systems. The monitored parameters include temperature, humidity, hive weight, sounds produced by bees, and the concentration of carbon dioxide (CO₂). The study examines how various sensor measurements reflect the condition of the bee colony and its interaction with the surrounding environment.*

Keywords: *sensor systems, weight, sound signals, temperature, humidity, carbon dioxide, measurement, seasons, productivity.*

Introduction. Bees have a significant positive impact on the environment and human life. Their conservation is important not only for ecological reasons but also for the social and economic development of rural communities [1,17]. Bees not only produce honey, beeswax, royal jelly, bee venom and propolis, but also play a crucial role in plant pollination, increasing crop yields, preserving rare plant species, ensuring sustainable use of natural resources, improving environmental conditions, and expanding food sources. For these reasons, it is essential to develop solutions aimed at maintaining and supporting the healthy existence of bee populations in society [2].

Materials and Methods. The research was conducted within the framework of the international project entitled “Smart-AI: Application of Smart Bee Colony System Technology and Development and Improvement of Beekeeping Resources in Uzbekistan in Cooperation with the Republic of Korea”. The experiments were carried out at the ART-BEE-TECH beekeeping complex in Qibray district of Tashkent region, at the G‘ulomxo‘ja Beekeeping farm, and at the educational and experimental farm of Tashkent State Agrarian University. Using project funds, Smart-AI smart bee colony system technology supplied to Uzbekistan by the South Korean organization Beonfarm was installed at these facilities.

Within this system, each experimental bee colony was equipped with smart sensors designed to measure parameters such as hive temperature, humidity, total hive weight (including honey, nectar, water, pollen, frames, and live bees), acoustic signals, and carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentration. The results could be conveniently monitored online via smartphones and computers.

During the study, each experimental bee colony at the above-mentioned facilities was examined and analyzed using this system, and the results were compared. Real-time monitoring of internal hive processes made it possible to study indicators such as colony strength development, theft incidents, honey collection activity, shortages of reserve food, and reductions in bee population caused by diseases [8,9].

Figure 1 – Connection of the bee module and the queen (master) module to the remote server

As shown in Figure 1, the Smart-AI bee colony system technology consists of two main modules. The first is referred to as the bee module, which is installed in the experimental hives at each apiary. The second is known as the queen (master) module; it is a central unit placed near the colonies and is capable of collecting data from all bee modules installed in the experimental hives at each site. The bee module is built on a Raspberry Pi 3B platform and is equipped with a Behringer UCA22 sound card (Music Tribe, Manchester, United Kingdom), two ADMP401 MEMS microphones (Analog Devices, Norwood, MA, USA), and two DHT22 sensors for measuring temperature and humidity (Aosong Electronics, Guangzhou, China).

The queen module includes sensors for measuring hive weight and carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentration, as well as several additional sensors used to record weather parameters in the vicinity of the hives. It is also based on a Raspberry Pi 3B and incorporates an Ethernet switch that enables communication with a remote server via a 5-GHz wireless bridge, allowing the collected data to be transmitted, processed, and stored. The system was installed between 27 and 29 May 2023 and has been operating continuously since then. All system components are connected to the mains power supply. The power consumption of the bee module is 4.24 W, while the queen module consumes 4 W [13,15]. The obtained data were subjected to statistical analysis using Student's t-test according to the methodology of Ye.K. Merkureva (1970, 1991), based on the correlation coefficient (R) values. All calculations and correlation analyses were performed on a computer using MS Office (Microsoft Excel) software.

Research Results. By analyzing the measurement data obtained from bee colonies located in beekeeping farms equipped with the Smart-AI smart bee colony system technology, various conditions related to the life and activity of bees were observed. In particular, the study examined the continuous daily activity of bees, weekly honey collection when comparing two seasons—spring and summer—and the process of colony strength development recorded in two hives [15].

During the period of continuous bee activity, hive weight, internal carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentration, temperature, and relative humidity were measured and analyzed over a full 24-hour cycle during two different periods of the year.

Diagram 1 – Measurements of hive weight and feed consumption during the winter season

As shown in Diagram 1, measurements were carried out on 10 February 2024, representing the winter season. During this period, the average daily hive weight was 31.3 kg in the control group, 47.2 kg in the first experimental group, and 35.8 kg in the second experimental group. The first experimental group showed a higher hive weight by 8.7 kg compared to the second experimental group and by 15.9 kg compared to the control group. At 06:00, the hive weight was 31.4 kg in the control group, 47.3 kg in the first experimental group, and 38.6 kg in the second experimental group, whereas at 21:00, the values were 31.1 kg, 47.0 kg, and 38.3 kg, respectively. During the winter season, bees do not leave the hive, and the gradual decrease in hive weight indicates that colonies consume their stored reserves to sustain themselves. The daily feed consumption amounted to 245 g in the control group, 290 g in the first experimental group, and 263 g in the second experimental group. The first experimental group consumed 27 g more feed than the second experimental group and 45 g more than the control group.

This can be explained by the larger number of worker bees and their higher level of activity in the first experimental group. It should be noted that daily feed consumption reached its peak between 12:00 and 15:00, when ambient temperature increased. During this period, feed consumption ranged from 50.8–60 g in the control group, 65–71 g in the first experimental group, and 55–66 g in the second experimental group. The scientific results obtained in this study are consistent with the findings of Italian researchers Stefania Ceschi et al. (2020), Indian researchers Anand N. et al. (2018), as well as A.I. Kasyanov (2003), Kozyaychev Yu.V. and Tkhorikov B.A. (2018), Yeskov Ye.K. and Yeskova M.D. (2018), and Eshdavlatov O.Z. (2021) [1,2,3,4,5,7,11,15].

As shown in Diagram 2, hive weight measurements for the summer season were recorded on 14 June 2024. During this period, the average daily hive weight was 58 kg in the control group, 75.1 kg in the first experimental group, and 69.7 kg in the second experimental group. The first experimental group demonstrated a higher value by 5.4 kg compared to the second experimental group and by 17.1 kg compared to the control group. At 06:00, the hive weight was 60 kg in the control group, 76 kg in the first experimental group, and 71 kg in the second experimental group, while at 21:00 the values increased to 63 kg, 82.1 kg, and 76.3 kg, respectively. During summer days, worker bees leave the hive between 09:00 and 15:00 to collect pollen and nectar, which leads to a temporary decrease in hive weight. In the evening, between 18:00 and 21:00, bees return to the hive, resulting in a slight increase in weight by the end of the day. This pattern reflects active foraging behavior and indicates effective regulation of colony strength.

Diagram 2 – Hive weight measurements during the summer season

Diagram 3 – Measurements of carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentration (ppm) in the hive during the winter season

As shown in Diagram 3, measurements were conducted on 10 February 2024, representing the winter season. During this period, the average daily concentration of carbon dioxide (CO₂) inside the hive was 244.3 ppm in the control group, 255.7 ppm in the first experimental group, and 249.3 ppm in the second experimental group. The first experimental group exhibited CO₂ levels that were 6.4 ppm higher than those of the second experimental group and 11.4 ppm higher than those of the control group. At 06:00, CO₂ concentrations were 240 ppm in the control group, 250 ppm in the first experimental group, and 245 ppm in the second experimental group. By 21:00, these values decreased slightly to 235 ppm, 245 ppm, and 242 ppm, respectively.

In both the control and experimental groups, CO₂ concentrations increased between 09:00 and 15:00, reaching their peak at 15:00. At this time, CO₂ levels reached 252 ppm in the control group and 268 ppm in both the first and second experimental groups.

During this period, the first experimental group showed values that were 12 ppm higher than those of the second experimental group and 16 ppm higher than those of the control group. This increase can be attributed to extended daylight hours and rising ambient temperatures, which enhanced bee activity, leading to higher oxygen consumption and increased production of carbon dioxide.

Diagram 4 – Measurements of carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentration (ppm) in the hive during the summer season

As shown in Diagram 4, based on measurements conducted on 14 June 2024 during the summer season, the average daily carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentration inside the hive was 2193 ppm in the control group, 2628.8 ppm in the first experimental group, and 2544.7 ppm in the second experimental group. The first experimental group demonstrated CO₂ levels that were 84.1 ppm higher than those of the second experimental group and 435.8 ppm higher than those of the control group. At 06:00, CO₂ concentrations were 2100 ppm in the control group, 2600 ppm in the first experimental group, and 2500 ppm in the second experimental group. By 21:00, these values changed to 2220 ppm, 2450 ppm, and 2310 ppm, respectively. In both the control and experimental groups, CO₂ concentrations increased between 09:00 and 15:00, reaching their maximum at 15:00. At this time, CO₂ levels reached 2280 ppm in the control group, 2764 ppm in the first experimental group, and 2708 ppm in the second experimental group.

During this period, the first experimental group exhibited values that were 56 ppm higher than those of the second experimental group and 484 ppm higher than those of the control group. According to the research findings, the concentration of carbon dioxide (CO₂) inside the hive is influenced by several factors, including ambient air temperature, increased humidity, the amount of brood present, the number of bees in the hive, and overall air quality.

Diagram 5 – Temperature measurements at the core (cluster center) of the bee colony during the winter season

As shown in Diagram 5, temperature measurements at the core of the bee colony during the winter season are presented. In winter, the average core temperature of the colony was +18.1°C in the control group, +20.8°C in the first experimental group, and +19.7°C in the second experimental group. The first experimental group showed temperatures that were +1.1°C higher than those of the second experimental group and +2.7°C higher than those of the control group. In both the control and experimental groups, temperatures increased between 09:00 and 15:00, reaching their maximum at 15:00. At this time, the temperatures were +21.2°C in the control group, +25.2°C in the first experimental group, and +25.6°C in the second experimental group. During this period, the first experimental group recorded temperatures that were +1.6°C higher than those of the second experimental group and +4.0°C higher than those of the control group. The results obtained in this study are consistent with the findings reported by Z. M. Sidiqov (2021) and O. Z. Eshdavlatov (2021) [4,14].

Diagram 6 – Hive temperature measurements during the summer season

As shown in Diagram 6, temperature measurements at the center of brood frames inside the hive during the summer season are presented. During summer, the average temperature at the center of brood frames was +32.6°C in the control group, +34.3°C in the first experimental group, and +33.9°C in the second experimental group. The first experimental group recorded temperatures that were +0.4°C higher than those of the second experimental group and +1.7°C higher than those of the control group. In both the control and experimental groups, temperatures increased between 09:00 and 15:00. During this period, the temperature at the center of brood frames reached +35°C in all groups. The results indicate that during the summer season, bees maintain a stable temperature at the center of brood frames, ensuring timely and proper development of the brood. Prolonged temperatures above +35°C or below +30°C during summer may result in underdevelopment or mortality of the brood.

As shown in Diagram 7, analysis of relative humidity variations measured over a 24-hour period on 10 February 2024 during the winter season made it possible to observe the continuous activity of bee colonies. In winter, the average relative humidity at the core of the colony was 55.8% in the control group, 60.4% in the first experimental group, and 58.3% in the second experimental group. The first experimental group showed values that were 2.1% higher than those of the second experimental group and 4.6% higher than those of the control group. In both the control and experimental groups, relative humidity decreased between 09:00 and 15:00 as daily temperature increased. The research results indicate that relative humidity is influenced by air temperature, day length, oxygen concentration, hive ventilation conditions, and the duration of

precipitation. During the winter season, bees overwinter successfully when relative humidity is maintained at approximately 50–65%.

Diagram 7 – Relative humidity measurements in the hive during the winter season

Diagram 8 – Relative humidity measurements in the hive during the summer season

Analysis of relative humidity variations measured over a 24-hour period on 14 June 2024 allowed observation of the daily activity of bee colonies. During the summer season, the average relative humidity between brood frames was 60.4% in the control group, 69.1% in the first experimental group, and 65.4% in the second experimental group. The first experimental group exhibited values that were 3.7% higher than those of the second experimental group and 8.7% higher than those of the control group.

In both the control and experimental groups, relative humidity decreased between 09:00 and 15:00 as daily temperature increased. A noticeable decline was observed during the central part of the day, which was more pronounced in summer when bees leave the hive to collect pollen and nectar. This pattern is associated with a reduced number of bees remaining inside the hive during this period, leading to lower humidity levels.

As shown in Diagram 9, changes in hive weight were observed over a one-week period from 16 to 22 May 2024 during the spring season. In spring, the average hive weight was 47.4 kg in the control group, 55.78 kg in the first experimental group, and 51.7 kg in the second experimental group. The first experimental group showed values that were 4.1 kg higher than those of the second experimental group and 8.4 kg higher than those of the control group. During the spring season, hive weight exhibited a fluctuating pattern as bees actively consumed honey. A consistent difference of 2–6 kg was maintained between the control and experimental groups, while by the end of the week, an overall weight increase of 4–8 kg was recorded in all groups.

Diagram 9 – Hive weight measurements during the spring season

Diagram 10 – Hive weight measurements during the summer season

As shown in Diagram 10, changes in hive weight were recorded over a one-week period from 15 to 21 June 2024 during the summer season. Over the course of the week, the average hive weight was 62.5 kg in the control group, 70.2 kg in the first experimental group, and 67.3 kg in the second experimental group. The first experimental group exceeded the second experimental group by 2.9 kg and the control group by 7.7 kg on average. With the onset of the main honey flow in summer, hive weight increased steadily. In the control group, the average hive weight at the beginning of the week was 50.4 kg, increasing to 75.1 kg by the end of the week, representing a total gain of 24.7 kg. In the first experimental group, hive weight increased from 56.2 kg at the beginning of the week to 85.6 kg at the end of the week, resulting in a total increase of 29.4 kg. Similarly, in the second experimental group, hive weight rose from 54.4 kg to 80.8 kg, with an overall increase of 26.4 kg during the same period. By the end of the observation period, the first experimental group showed hive weights that were 3.0 kg higher than those of the second experimental group and 4.7 kg higher than those of the control group, indicating more intensive honey accumulation and stronger colony development during the summer season.

On 15 April 2024, changes in hive weight recorded over a single day during a swarming event in one colony showed that at 10:00, the total hive weight was 43 kg. After swarming occurred, the hive weight decreased to 40 kg at 11:00 and remained at this level during the subsequent hours. The sharp reduction in hive weight of up to 3 kg during the spring season clearly

indicates that a portion of the bees left the hive to form a swarm. Swarming begins in spring as a result of an increase in the number of bees in the hive and a rise in the daily egg-laying activity of the queen. This process represents a natural reproductive strategy of the bee colony. When anticipated in advance and managed properly, swarming can provide beekeepers with a positive opportunity to increase the number of colonies by preserving and establishing new hives.

Diagram 11 – Swarming of a bee colony on 15 April 2024

Diagram 12 – Formation of a swarm in a bee colony and its impact on the colony on 8 June 2024

On 8 June 2024, changes in hive weight recorded over the course of one day during a swarming event in a single colony showed that at 08:00, the total hive weight was 73 kg. After the formation of the swarm, the hive weight decreased to 67.5 kg at 09:00, reached 67 kg at 10:00, and remained at this level during the subsequent hours. The sharp reduction in hive weight of up to 5.5 kg during the summer season clearly indicates that a significant portion of the bees left the hive to form a swarm. This process is characterized by two key indicators: a sudden change in hive weight and an increase in acoustic signals during the swarming event.

Diagram 13 – Sound signal measurements in a bee colony before and after swarming on 15 April 2024

On 15 April 2024, sound signal measurements recorded inside a single bee colony over the course of one day during a swarming event showed that the velocity of the recorded sound waves

increased to 1.5 km/s at 10:00. From 11:00 onward, the sound wave velocity returned to a stable level of 1.0 km/s, indicating the restoration of a calm state within the colony after the swarming event.

Diagram 14 – Sound signal measurements in a bee colony before and after swarming on 8 June 2024

On 8 June 2024, sound signal measurements recorded inside a single bee colony over the course of one day during a swarming event showed that the velocity of the recorded sound waves increased sharply to 5.0 km/s at 09:00. From 10:00 onward, the sound wave velocity returned to a stable baseline level of 1.0 km/s, indicating a return to a calm state within the colony. According to the research results, the swarming process is closely associated with acoustic measurements and corresponds to a significant increase in sound activity during swarm formation.

Diagram 15 – Average annual temperature indicators inside the beehive

As shown in Diagram 15, the average annual internal temperature of the beehives in both the experimental and control groups reached +34°C in March, coinciding with the onset of egg-laying by the queen bees. During this period, the temperature around the frames averaged +30°C. During the period of intensive egg-laying by the queens, namely in April, May, and June, the average temperature at the center of the brood frames reached +35°C (35 ± 0.5°C). These values were consistent and statistically reliable in both experimental groups, with a correlation coefficient of $R > 0.999$. In July, the average temperature in the core area of the hive increased to +40°C, during which time the queen bees completely ceased egg-laying. In August and September, as ambient temperatures decreased to an average of +34–35°C, egg-laying activity resumed. In October, the average temperature dropped to +25°C, and the queen bees again stopped laying eggs. These observations indicate that deviations of temperature above or below the optimal range have

a direct impact on brood development. The findings of this study are consistent with the conclusions reported by Ye.K. Yeskov and M.D. Yeskova (2017), I.Z. Ochoa, S. Gutierrez, and F. Rodríguez (2019), and N.N. Kharchenko and V.E. Rindin (2003) [2,3,13,16].

Diagram 16 – Average annual relative humidity inside the beehive

According to the data presented in Diagram 16, the annual relative humidity inside the beehives of both the experimental and control groups averaged 50% during January and February. As bees began bringing nectar into the hive, relative humidity gradually increased, reaching 60% in March, approximately 65% in April, and 70% in May and June. In July, relative humidity decreased slightly to 65%, while in August and September it declined to 50%. During October, November, and December, the average relative humidity dropped further to approximately 40%. During the main nectar flow period of bee colonies, from April to July, the average relative humidity ranged between 65–70% ($65 \pm 5\%$). These values were statistically reliable in both experimental groups, with a correlation coefficient of $R > 0.99$. The results of this study are consistent with the findings reported by H. Human, S.W. Nicolson, and V. Dietemann (2006), N.N. Kharchenko and V.E. Rindin (2003), and O.Z. Eshdavlatov (2021) [4,6,10,11]. The average annual concentration of carbon dioxide (CO_2) inside the beehive is not constant and may vary throughout the season depending on colony size and hive ventilation. However, it generally ranges from 0.1% (1000 ppm) to 3–5% (30,000–50,000 ppm), reaching its highest levels under conditions of high colony density and poor ventilation [16].

Diagram 17 – Average annual carbon dioxide (CO_2) concentration inside the beehive

According to the results of this study, the average annual concentration of carbon dioxide (CO₂) in both the experimental and control groups reached 2564 ppm in April. Over the course of the year, CO₂ levels varied within the range of 400–2564 ppm, depending on colony size and the efficiency of hive ventilation. The overall average annual CO₂ concentration inside the beehive was 1272 ppm. These findings are consistent with the conclusions reported by H. Human, S.W. Nicolson, and V. Dietemann (2006) and V.I. Korishev (2014) [6,12].

Conclusion

The results demonstrate that real-time, long-term monitoring of indicators such as daily bee activity, weekly honey accumulation, seasonal comparisons between spring and summer, swarming events recorded in two hives, and annual variations in temperature, relative humidity, and carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentration plays a crucial role in the continuous monitoring of bee colonies. The collected data provide valuable insights that support the efficient management and effective utilization of bee colonies in modern beekeeping.

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